

C# DASTURINING MUHITI VA MASALALARNI SINIF TIPIDA ISHLASH KO'NIKMALARI

Gavharoy Soliyeva Yodgorjon qizi

Namangan davlat universiteti Amaliy matematika va raqamli texnologiyalari
kafedrası o'qituvchisi,
soliyevagavharoy000@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada C# dasturining tarixi va muhiti yoritib berilib, arifmetik progressiya va geometrik progressiyalarni class tipida hal qildik.

Kalit so'zlar: Class, klassning xususiyati, class maydoni, class nomi, arifmetik va geometric progressiya.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается история и среда программы C#, и мы решили арифметические и геометрические прогрессии в типе класса.

Ключевые слова: Класс, свойство класса, поле класса, имя класса, арифметическая и геометрическая прогрессия.

Annotation: This article covers the history and environment of C# programming, and we solved arithmetic progressions and geometric progressions in class type.

Keywords: Class, class property, class field, class name, arithmetic and geometric progression.

Kirish. Hozirgi zamonaviy dunyoyimizda C# dasturlash tilining o'rni beqiyosdir. Dastlab C# dasturining kelib chiqishi 2000-yillarga borib taqaladi. Barcha dasturlash tillarida eng ahamiyatli o'rinlarda turadigan class tushunchasi bo'lib, C⁴⁷lass – bu dastur tomonidan aniqlanadigan tip bo'lib, unda ma'lumotlarning tuzilmasi va ularni qayta ishlashga mo'ljallangan funksiyalar birlashtiriladi. Bu ma'lumotlar **klassning xususiyatlari**, funksiyalar esa **maydonlari** deb ataladi. Klasslar dasturda nomi, xususiyatlari va metodlarini ko'rsatish orqali aniqlanadi. Bu jarayon maxsus shablon ostida amalga oshiriladi. Klasslar yordamida dasturda xuddi int, char kabi yangi obyektlarni tashkil qilish va qayta ishlash mumkin. Mazkur jarayon umumiy holda quyidagi sxema ostida amalga oshiriladi:

⁴⁷ Troelsen, P. Japikse. Pro C# 8 with .NET Core. Foundational Principles and Practices in Programming. Apress, 2020

class class_nomi

{ Klass elementlarining (xususiyatlari) tavsifi;

Metodlar tavsifi; };

Dastlab ishimizning birinchi qadami **SharpDevelop** dasturini ishga tushirishdan boshlaymiz:

1-rasm

1-rasmda ko'rsatilgan oynadan **New solution** buyrug'ini tanlab olamiz. So'ngra hosil qilgan yangi oynamizga masala tipidan kelib chiqib nom beramiz.

Masala: Arifmetik progressiyaning birinchi hadi a_1 , hadlar ayirmasi d ga, hadlari n ta. Shu progressiyaning oxirgi hadi a_n va dastlabki n ta hadi yig'indisi S_n ni hisoblash dasturini yarating. Sinfda yarating va undan foydalaning.

Masala shartidan kelib chiqib biz dasturimizga **class_arifmetik** deb nomlab olamiz va create buyrug'ini tanlaymiz:

2-rasm

Natijada bizda quyidagi oyna hosil bo'ladi:

3-rasm

Dasturi:

```
using System;
```

```
namespace class_arifmetik
```

```
{
```

```
class Program
```

```
{
```

```
public static void Main(string[] args)
```

```
{
```

```
Console.WriteLine("Arifmetik progressiya uchun dastur");
```

```
Console.WriteLine("-----");
```

```
Console.WriteLine();
```

```
Console.Write("Ilk had (a1) ni kiriting: ");
```

```
int a1 = Convert.ToInt32(Console.ReadLine());
```

```
Console.Write("Ayirma (d) ni kiriting: ");
```

```
int d = Convert.ToInt32(Console.ReadLine());
```

```
Console.Write("Hadlar sonini (n) kiriting: ");
```

```
int n = Convert.ToInt32(Console.ReadLine());
```

```
// Arifmetik progressiyaning oxirgi hadini hisoblash
```

```
int an = a1 + (n - 1) * d;
```

```
// Dastlabki n ta hadining yig'indisini hisoblash
```

```
int Sn = (n * (a1 + an)) / 2;
```

```
Console.WriteLine();
```

```
Console.WriteLine("Arifmetik progressiyaning oxirgi hadi (an): " + an);
```

```
Console.WriteLine("Dastlabki n ta hadining yig'indisi (Sn): " + Sn);
```

```
Console.ReadLine();
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

Dastur kodini kompyuter xotirasiga kiritib olamiz:


```
class_arifmetik - SharpDevelop
File Edit View Refactor Project Build Debug Search Analysis Tools Window Help
Default layout
Program.cs
class_arifmetik.Program
Main(string[] args)
9 using System;
10
11 namespace class_arifmetik
12 {
13     class Program
14     {
15         public static void Main(string[] args)
16         {
17             Console.WriteLine("Arifmetik progressiya uchun dastur");
18             Console.WriteLine("-----");
19             Console.WriteLine();
20
21             Console.Write("Ilk had (a1) ni kiriting: ");
22             int a1 = Convert.ToInt32(Console.ReadLine());
23
24             Console.Write("Ayirma (d) ni kiriting: ");
25             int d = Convert.ToInt32(Console.ReadLine());
26
27             Console.Write("Hadlar sonini (n) kiriting: ");
28             int n = Convert.ToInt32(Console.ReadLine());
29
30             // Arifmetik progressiyaning oxirgi hadini hisoblash
31             int an = a1 + (n - 1) * d;
32
33             // Dastlabki n ta hadining yig'indisini hisoblash
34             int Sn = (n * (a1 + an)) / 2;
35
36             Console.WriteLine();
37             Console.WriteLine("Arifmetik progressiyaning oxirgi hadi (an): " + an);
38             Console.WriteLine("Dastlabki n ta hadining yig'indisi (Sn): " + Sn);
39
40             Console.ReadLine();
41         }
42     }
43 }
```

4-rasm

Natija olamiz:


```
Arifmetik progressiya uchun dastur
-----
Ilk had (a1) ni kiriting: 3
Ayirma (d) ni kiriting: 2
Hadlar sonini (n) kiriting: 9

Arifmetik progressiyaning oxirgi hadi (an): 19
Dastlabki n ta hadining yig'indisi (Sn): 99
```

5-rasm

Masala-2

Geometrik progressiyaning birinchi hadi b_1 , mahraji $q(q>1)$ ga, hadlari n ta. Shu geometric progressiyaning oxirgi hadi b_n va dastlabki n ta hadi yig'indisi S_n ni hisoblash dasturini yarating. Sinfda yarating va undan foydalaning.

Dasturi:

using System;

class GeometricProgression

```
{
    private double b1; //          birinchi          had
    private double q; //          mahraj
    private int n; //          hadlar          soni

    public GeometricProgression(double b1, double q, int n)
    {
        this.b1 = b1;
        this.q = q;
        this.n = n;
    }

    public double CalculateBn()
    {
        return b1 * Math.Pow(q, n - 1); //          oxirgi          had
    }

    public double CalculateSn()
    {
        return (b1 * (Math.Pow(q, n) - 1)) / (q - 1); //          dastlabki          n          ta          hadi          yig'indisi
    }
}
```

class Program

```
{
    static void Main(string[] args)
    {
        Console.WriteLine("Geometrik progressiyaning birinchi hadini kiriting (b1): ");
        double b1 = Convert.ToDouble(Console.ReadLine());

        Console.WriteLine("Mahrajni kiriting (q > 1): ");
        double q = Convert.ToDouble(Console.ReadLine());

        Console.WriteLine("Hadlar sonini kiriting (n): ");
        int n = Convert.ToInt32(Console.ReadLine());

        GeometricProgression progression = new GeometricProgression(b1, q, n);
        double bn = progression.CalculateBn();
        double sn = progression.CalculateSn();
    }
}
```

```

Console.WriteLine("Progressiyaning oxirgi hadi (bn): " + bn);
Console.WriteLine("Dastlabki {0} ta hadi yig'indisi (Sn): {1}", n, sn);
Console.ReadKey();
}
}

```

Dasturni kompyuter xotirasiga kiritamiz:

6-rasm

7-rasm

Natijasi:

```
Geometrik progressiyaning birinchi hadini kiriting (b?):  
2  
Mahrajni kiriting (q > 1):  
3  
Hadlar sonini kiriting (n):  
3  
Progressiyaning oxirgi hadi (bn): 18  
Dastlabki 3 ta hadi yig'indisi (Sn): 26
```

8-rasm

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

1. <http://dasturchi.uz>
2. <http://uzbekdevs.uz>
3. Троелсен Эндрю, Жепикс Филипп | Язык программирования C# 7 и платформы .NET и .NET Core. Вильямс. 2018.
4. Troelsen, P. Japikse. Pro C# 8 with .NET Core. Foundational Principles and Practices in Programming. Apress, 2020
5. <https://www.bestprog.net/ru/2018/12/13/built-in-classes-built-in-static-classes-declaring-and-using-built-in-classes-examples-ru/> - Ichki sinflardan foydalanish